

THE EFFECTIVE WAYS OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS

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Annotation. This article highlights some further information how to develop learners' speaking skills and discusses some new and experienced ideas given by some experts. Besides it provides some useful methods of improving and developing of speaking as a skill and a habit.

Key words: communication, authenticity, source language, target language, speech patterns

According to Lai Mei Leong and Seyedeh Masoumeh Ahmadi, "Speaking is one of the most important skills to be developed and enhanced as means of effective communication. Speaking skill is regarded one of the most difficult aspects of language learning. Many language learners find it difficult to express themselves in spoken language. They are generally facing problems to use the foreign language to express their thoughts effectively". Foundation is the basis of learning any language. When we have a strong foundation learning a language, we don't need any supper ways given by some EFL teachers to improve it. Because the best tip to develop our speaking is ourselves. As Rivers (1981) argues, speaking is used twice as much as reading and writing in our communication.

Firstly, we have to expand our vocabulary and at the same time we will know the correct pronunciation of the word. While, we practice these both together, the natural flow of English words begins to come to us easily. After having reached a point that we can speak, we have got only speaking confidentiality. Selcuk Koran said, "Many of the learners are anxious to speak in the classroom or outside it due to different social or psychological reasons, so they keep silent. Therefore, it is

necessary for language teachers to implement some natural strategies such as: role plays, group work, projects, etc. to avoid shyness and unwillingness to speak English". The only way of building confidence within ourselves is practice speaking more and more with some strategies.

However, anyone cannot do it. At that point, we will approach some great effective tips to speak better in English. Once we search some techniques of developing our skills, we can come across thousands of it. But which one works best, let's look at the following effective ones:

1. Learn phrases, not single words. Learning separate words is a very common mistake learners usually have. And of course, it's not an appropriate method to learn any language, not just English. Knowing the meanings of words is useful. But knowing how to use them in context is even more important. For example, "take a picture" not "make a picture" because it deals with the combination of words. Learning phrases seems like the smart way, since once you're familiar with the word chain, you may speak naturally and automatically; so, your communication may go more smoothly and learning phrases is somehow learning grammar. There are different types of phrases podcasts, newspapers, stories, audio books, movies, or songs.

2. Listen to more English. Another way is focus on more listening rather than reading. Learn with your ears, not your eyes. By listening students can enlarge their vocabulary, grammar and materials should be authentic. Students can find materials from TED talks, BBC English news, cartoons and movies, songs, audiobooks.

3 Practice thinking in English. Translating from Source language to Target language is most of learners' common mistake. They have to stop it right now and start to think in English when they speak English. It will be difficult for beginners then they will be in the process and everything will be alright. Everything needs practicing and students can start with some pieces like "let's go", "dinner's ready, come and get it", "good job. You did it", "come on", "come in". In addition to this they can use English-English dictionary while doing home tasks.

4. Learn deeply. A common issue of English learners is that they only try to learn as many language items as they can, yet never review them later on. That is why most of learners cannot remember words, phrases and sentence patterns while speaking. A study has shown that people forget 40% of what they learned in 20 minutes, 77% of what they learned in six days and 90% after one month. It means that short-term memory can't store things for so long. When any learners don't spend time memorizing things, they will fade away from their memory easily. What does that mean by learning deeply? Well, learning deeply means they repeat something many, many times over again until they master it.

Taking these points into consideration, these ways may help to increase students' speaking skill. If they follow through with these 4 tips within 3 or 4 months every student will notice a big difference in their confidence and fluency.

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